

Supplement. eMethods: model development and validation detail

This supplement expands the Methods sections “Prediction models” and “Validation and performance.” All settings are fixed in the analysis code (`scripts/_models.py`); random seed 42 throughout.

Nested cross-validation

Performance was estimated by nested cross-validation with 5 outer folds and 3 inner folds, stratified jointly by the binary outcome and the four US Census regions. When a joint stratum held fewer than 10 observations, the fold assignment fell back to outcome-only stratification for that stratum. Outer-fold predictions were pooled out of fold before computing performance, so no observation contributed to both training and evaluation of the prediction that scored it. All preprocessing (survey-weighted imputation of missing predictors, one-hot encoding, and scaling) was fit on the inner or outer training partition only and applied to the held-out partition, so no information from held-out records entered training.

Gradient boosting: search space and fitting

The gradient boosting model (XGBoost, binary logistic objective) was tuned by random search over 12 candidate configurations per outer fold, each scored by the mean survey-weighted AUC across the 3 inner folds. During the search, candidates were fit with 300 boosting rounds. The selected configuration was then refit on the full outer-training partition with up to 600 boosting rounds and early stopping after 20 rounds without improvement on a 10% stratified internal validation split; across the five outer folds the retained models used 227 to 485 rounds. Survey weights, normalized to a mean of 1, were supplied as observation weights; no `scale_pos_weight` or other class-balancing term was used, to keep predictions calibrated to population risk.

Random-search space:

Hyperparameter	Sampled values
<code>max_depth</code>	3, 4, 5, 6
<code>learning_rate</code>	0.02, 0.05, 0.1
<code>min_child_weight</code>	1, 5, 10

Hyperparameter	Sampled values
subsample	0.7, 0.8, 1.0
colsample_bytree	0.7, 0.8, 1.0
reg_lambda	0.5, 1.0, 2.0
boosting rounds (search / refit)	300 / up to 600 with early stopping (20 rounds)

Penalized logistic benchmark (LASSO)

The L1-penalized logistic benchmark used the saga solver with categorical predictors one-hot encoded (first level dropped) so coefficients remain interpretable. The inverse penalty strength was selected by 3-fold inner cross-validation over six log-spaced values (0.001, 0.0063, 0.0398, 0.2512, 1.5849, 10.0), with convergence tolerance $1e-3$. Survey weights entered as observation weights.

Spline logistic benchmark

The fair linear benchmark modeled age with a restricted cubic spline (Harrell parameterization, 4 knots) placed at the survey-weighted 0.05, 0.35, 0.65, and 0.95 quantiles of age, recomputed within each training fold; if fewer than 4 distinct knots resulted, equally spaced knots were used as a fallback. The spline basis was combined with the one-hot-encoded social determinants in an unpenalized logistic model (lbfgs). This benchmark isolates whether the gradient boosting advantage reflects interactions and nonadditivity rather than the absence of a flexible age term.

Performance and calibration

Discrimination was the survey-weighted AUC and calibration the survey-weighted Brier score, each with a 95% confidence interval from a design-based bootstrap that resampled primary sampling units within strata, matching the survey estimand. The unweighted DeLong interval was computed as a secondary reference on the unweighted AUC. Calibration was further summarized by the survey-weighted calibration intercept and slope and by a weighted, decile-binned calibration plot (Figure S1). The incremental value of the social determinants over age was the difference in weighted AUC between the full model and an age-only restricted cubic spline, tested by a paired design-based bootstrap. Equity was assessed by re-estimating weighted discrimination and calibration within strata defined by race/ethnicity, household income,

and insurance (Figure 3), and decision curve analysis expressed the net benefit of risk-based outreach across threshold probabilities (Figure S3).

Explainability

TreeSHAP produced a global summary of mean absolute SHAP values, with age shown separately from the social determinants, computed on a stratified weighted subsample to preserve small subgroups (Figure S2). Pairwise SHAP interaction values ranked the determinant pairs with the largest joint contributions. Because a SHAP interaction magnitude is not a test of statistical super-additivity, the four pre-specified pairs were tested for departure from a multiplicative null with a survey-weighted logistic product-term model, the product-term coefficient estimated on the log-odds scale with a design-based bootstrap that resampled primary sampling units within strata.

Final model for explanation, and ranking stability

The global explanations were computed on a single model refit on the full established-eligible cohort, separate from the cross-validated models used for performance. That deployment model took the hyperparameters selected in the first outer fold (max_depth 4, learning rate 0.02, minimum child weight 5, subsample 0.7, column subsample 1.0, L2 penalty 2.0) and was fit with a fixed 600 boosting rounds and no early stopping, whereas the cross-validated models were early-stopped at 227 to 485 rounds. To confirm that the determinant ranking did not depend on that single configuration, we refit the model with the median hyperparameters across the five outer folds (max_depth 3, learning rate 0.05, minimum child weight 1, subsample 0.7, column subsample 1.0, L2 penalty 1.0) and recomputed the grouped mean absolute SHAP values on the same weighted subsample. The two rankings agreed closely (Spearman correlation 0.97; Kendall tau 0.93), with the same five predictors leading. The only change was a reordering inside the narrowly spaced education, age, and income block at the top, the same near-tie seen between the path-dependent and interventional algorithms. This check is reproduced by `scripts/_f17_shap_stability.py`, writes `results/eligible/f17_shap_stability.json`, and overwrites no production artifact.

External temporal validation (BRFSS 2022)

As an external test in time, the final gradient boosting model trained on the 2024 established-eligible cohort was applied, without retraining or recalibration, to the 2022 BRFSS, the preceding even survey year in which the colorectal cancer screening items were likewise in the rotating core. The 2022 records were recoded to the 2024 analytic schema. The screening recommendation variable (`_CRCREC2` in 2022) carried the same three eligible states as the 2024 variable (up to date, overdue, never screened) over the

same 45-to-75 eligibility range, and the insurance variable (`_HLTHPLN`) was populated at all ages including 65 years and older, so the Medicare-age band was not lost; no predictor required a different coding. The 2024 preprocessor imputed any missing predictor with the weighted mode or median learned on 2024, matching deployment. Weighted AUC, weighted Brier score, and the weighted calibration intercept and slope were computed on the 2022 eligible cohort with the same design-based bootstrap that resampled primary sampling units within the 2022 strata. The model was applied as fixed; no 2022 outcomes were used to adjust it.

Multiple imputation sensitivity for the interaction tests

The primary pipeline used a single survey-weighted imputation inside each fold, which understates the uncertainty from item non-response. We therefore ran a multiple-imputation sensitivity for the four pre-specified interaction tests. Twenty imputations were drawn by multivariate imputation by chained equations (scikit-learn `IterativeImputer` with posterior sampling) over the incomplete predictor codes, with imputed integers rounded and clipped to their valid range and the complete predictors entered as covariates. For each imputation the survey-weighted logistic product-term model was refit with the normalized weights as frequency weights, and the product-term coefficients were pooled by Rubin's rules, reporting the pooled log-odds coefficient, its 95% confidence interval, the two-sided P value, and the fraction of missing information. The per-imputation standard error is model-based and does not carry the primary sampling unit clustering, so these intervals are not interchangeable with the design-based primary tests; the sensitivity asks only whether item non-response, almost entirely in household income, changes the interaction conclusions.

Interventional SHAP and predictor association

The primary global SHAP summary used path-dependent TreeSHAP. Because that algorithm distributes credit along tree paths and can be sensitive to correlation among predictors, we recomputed the global summary with interventional TreeSHAP against a weighted background sample, which breaks the path dependence by integrating over a reference distribution. The two rankings were compared by the Spearman correlation of the per-predictor mean absolute SHAP values and by whether the education-versus-income order changed. To contextualize how credit was allocated among correlated determinants, a predictor association matrix was computed: the bias-corrected Cramér V for categorical pairs and the correlation ratio (η) for age against each categorical predictor, on complete unweighted pairs.

Intersectional MAIHDA

To quantify how much of the variation in delay sits between intersectional social strata, we fit a multilevel analysis of individual heterogeneity and discriminatory accuracy. Strata were defined by the cross-classification of education, household income, race/ethnicity, and sex. A null two-level logistic model with a random intercept for stratum gave the between-stratum variance on the logit scale and the variance partition coefficient, the share of the latent variation lying between strata. An adjusted model that added the additive main effects of the four stratifying variables gave the proportional change in variance, the share of between-stratum variance explained by the additive terms, with the residual reflecting the intersectional, non-additive component. Discriminatory accuracy was the AUC obtained by assigning each respondent the mean delay of their own stratum. Models were estimated by variational Bayes with a maximum a posteriori cross-check (statsmodels), unweighted, because the target is the structure of the strata rather than a population mean; this analysis complements the survey-weighted prediction model rather than replacing it. Variational Bayes slightly understates variance components relative to Markov chain Monte Carlo, which would if anything widen the residual intersectional share.

Software

Python 3.9.6 with pinned versions: numpy 1.26.2, pandas 2.1.4, scikit-learn 1.2.2, xgboost 2.0.2, shap 0.49.1, scipy 1.13.1, matplotlib 3.9.4, statsmodels 0.14.1. Seeds were fixed and the pipeline is reproducible end to end from a single command.